

Synthesis and Characterization of CaO Catalyst Prepared from Clamshell for Methanolysis of *Hura crepitans* Seeds Triglyceride to Biodiesel

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ABSTRACT

This study explores biodiesel production from sandbox tree (*Hura crepitans*) seed oil using a calcium oxide (CaO) catalyst derived from clamshells. The CaO catalyst was prepared through calcination at 900 °C, which decomposed carbonates into active CaO, and was characterized using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Energy-Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (EDXRF), X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis. The XRD pattern confirmed the predominance of CaO in the calcined clamshell, supported by EDXRF results. The biodiesel produced was evaluated for various fuel properties, including specific gravity: 0.83 ± 0.001 , saponification value: 24.76 ± 1.3 mgKOH/g, higher heating value: 53.69 ± 2.8 MJ/kg, kinematic viscosity: 3.43 ± 0.04 mm²/sec, flash point: 135 ± 2.61 °C, cloud point: 8.36 ± 0.57 °C, pour point: -3.89 ± 0.2 °C, acid value: 0.45 ± 0.01 mgKOH/g, and sulfur content: $0.01 \pm 0.001\%$. The results suggest that the clamshell-derived CaO catalyst is a viable and efficient heterogeneous catalyst for biodiesel production, offering a promising approach for sustainable energy generation and the utilization of waste materials.

Keywords: Biodiesel, calcium oxide catalyst, clamshell, *Hura crepitans*, transesterification

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INTRODUCTION

Calcium oxide, widely recognized as quicklime, is a multifaceted material that has garnered significant attention across various industrial sectors due to its broad applicability, particularly as a catalyst in biodiesel production. The conventional method of producing calcium oxide involves the calcination of limestone, a process that entails subjecting calcium carbonate to elevated temperatures, thereby yielding calcium oxide and carbon dioxide. Nonetheless, this traditional approach has raised concerns regarding its environmental sustainability, given that the depletion of non-renewable resources and the concomitant release of carbon dioxide emissions contribute to environmental degradation (Kedir *et al.*, 2023; Mignardi *et al.*, 2024). In light of these challenges, researchers have been prompted to explore alternative, more sustainable sources of calcium oxide that not only reduce environmental impact but also promote the efficient utilization of waste materials. One such promising alternative is the use of clamshells, an abundant waste product generated by the seafood industry. Clamshells, primarily composed of calcium

carbonate, can be transformed into calcium oxide through a calcination process similar to that used for limestone. This innovative approach offers a dual benefit: it provides a renewable source of calcium oxide while simultaneously addressing the environmental concerns associated with the disposal of clamshell waste (Kedir *et al.*, 2023; Mignardi *et al.*, 2024).

The utilization of clamshells as a source of calcium oxide embodies the principles of green chemistry and sustainable development. By converting waste materials into valuable resources, this method reduces the reliance on natural, non-renewable resources and minimizes waste disposal issues, thereby contributing to a more circular and sustainable economy. Moreover, the application of calcium oxide derived from clamshells in biodiesel production aligns with global efforts to develop more environmentally friendly and sustainable energy solutions (Mignardi *et al.*, 2024). The efficacy of calcium oxide as a catalyst in the production of biodiesel is contingent upon its physical and chemical properties, which are directly

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influenced by the source material and the synthesis process employed. Consequently, a comprehensive characterization of the synthesized calcium oxide is imperative to ascertain its suitability for catalysing the transesterification of sandbush tree seed oil or any other feedstock used in biodiesel production. This characterization ensures that the calcium oxide possesses the requisite properties to efficiently facilitate the transesterification reaction, thereby yielding biodiesel that meets the necessary standards for use as a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels (Alanis *et al.*, 2024).

The production of calcium oxide from clamshells presents a viable and sustainable alternative to traditional methods, offering both environmental and economic benefits. As the world continues to seek more sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions for energy production and waste management, the exploration and development of such innovative approaches are of paramount importance. This study aims to investigate the potential of calcium oxide derived from clamshells as a catalyst for biodiesel production, thus advancing sustainable energy solutions and strategies for waste reduction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and Treatment

Clamshells were randomly collected from the Lokobi area in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto. To prepare them for analysis, the clamshells underwent a series of processing steps: The clamshells were thoroughly washed to remove any impurities or debris, then, the washed clamshells were dried in an oven at 120°C for 10 hours to remove moisture, and finally, the dried clamshells were therefore ground into a fine powder using an electrical grinder. This preparation procedure follows established methods (Kedir *et al.*, 2023; Oraegbunam *et al.*, 2023), ensuring the clamshell powder is suitable for further analysis and use in subsequent experiments.

Catalyst Preparation and Characterization

The calcium oxide (CaO) catalyst was synthesized from the powdered clamshells prepared earlier. A 100g sample of clamshell powder was weighed into a crucible and placed in an electric furnace. The powder was calcined at 900°C for 3 hours to facilitate the thermal decomposition of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) into calcium oxide (CaO) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). After calcination, the sample was carefully removed from the furnace using tongs and transferred to a desiccator to cool, preventing exposure to atmospheric moisture and carbon dioxide. Once cooled, the calcined catalyst was ground into a fine powder using a milling machine to increase its surface area. The

powdered catalyst was then stored in an airtight container to maintain its integrity before analysis. The prepared CaO catalyst was characterized using various analytical techniques to determine its chemical composition, structural properties, and surface area. These techniques include FTIR, EDXRF, XRD, and BET. These characterization techniques provided valuable insights into the properties of the synthesized CaO catalyst, ensuring its suitability for catalytic applications.

Biodiesel Synthesis (Transesterification)

The oil underwent a pre-treatment step where it was heated to 120°C to evaporate any water content, ensuring optimal conditions for the subsequent transesterification reaction. This reaction was conducted in a 250cm³ two-neck round-bottom flask equipped with a reflux condenser to prevent methanol loss and maintain reaction pressure, a temperature controller to regulate the reaction temperature, and a magnetic stirrer to ensure thorough mixing of reactants. A suspension of methanol and CaO catalyst was added to the pre-heated oil (50g) in the reactor. The reactor was then immersed in a water bath, and the reaction conditions were maintained with constant stirring at 300 rpm. After the transesterification reaction was complete, the mixture was subjected to centrifugation to separate the catalyst-glycerol mixture from the biodiesel. The resulting mixture was then transferred to a separating funnel, allowing for the removal of the catalyst-glycerol phase from the biodiesel phase. This process facilitated the efficient production of biodiesel, with the CaO catalyst playing a crucial role in facilitating the transesterification reaction. The separated biodiesel was then ready for further analysis and characterization.

Determination of Fuel Properties of the Biodiesel

The fuel properties of the produced biodiesel were evaluated following American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) D methods for biodiesel fuel. These standardized tests ensured that the biodiesel met the required specifications for use as a fuel. The analysis included various parameters that define the quality and performance of biodiesel, such as cloud point, flash point, and pour point, among others. By adhering to ASTM D methods, the study provided a comprehensive assessment of the biodiesel's suitability for use in diesel engines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FTIR Spectrum of Raw Clamshell

The raw and calcined clamshell powders underwent FTIR analysis to identify the absorption bands associated with various functional groups present in the samples. This technique provided valuable insights

into the chemical composition and structural changes occurring in the clamshells before and after calcination. The FTIR spectra of the raw clamshell sample in Figure 1 and the calcined clamshell sample shown in Figure 2 were compared to determine the effects of calcination on the functional groups present.

By analysing these spectra, the study aimed to understand the transformation of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) to calcium oxide (CaO) and its implications for the catalytic activity of the clamshell-derived catalyst.

Figure 1: FTIR spectrum of Raw Clamshell

The FTIR spectra of the raw and calcined clamshell samples were recorded within the bandwidth of 600–4000 cm^{-1} . Both spectra exhibited several peaks, including a sharp peak at 711 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the stretching lattice vibration of the Ca–O bond, wide and strong peaks around 1401–1455 cm^{-1} and 857–872 cm^{-1} , assigned to asymmetric stretching of the C–O bond of unidentate carbonate species and absorption peak around 1785–1789 cm^{-1} (Krishnamurthy *et al.*, 2020). Notably, the raw clamshell spectrum in Figure 1 displayed an absorption peak at 1079 cm^{-1} , indicative of CO bending frequency in carbonates, confirming the presence of metal carbonates (Prajapati *et al.*, 2023). This peak suggests that CaCO_3 is the major component of the clamshell. The obtained infrared spectra results are consistent with those reported in previous studies.

Figure 2: FTIR spectrum of Calcined Clamshell

These findings validate the composition and structural properties of the clamshell samples, providing a foundation for further analysis and application.

EDXRF of Calcined Clamshell

The chemical composition of the calcined clamshell catalyst was evaluated using EDXRF spectroscopic analysis. The results, presented in Figure 3, provide insight into the elemental composition of the catalyst. This analysis helps to determine the presence and proportion of various elements, including calcium

(Ca) and other potential impurities, in the calcined clamshell sample. The EDXRF findings offer valuable information on the catalyst's chemical structure, which is essential for understanding its catalytic properties and potential applications.

The EDXRF analysis revealed that calcium is the predominant element in the calcined clamshell catalyst, present at a concentration of 92.65 wt. %. This high calcium content, primarily in the form of calcium oxide (CaO), serves as the active material for facilitating the conversion of triglycerides into methyl

esters during the transesterification process. The dominance of calcium in the catalyst composition indicates that the clamshells, primarily composed of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), were effectively converted to CaO through calcination. This transformation is crucial for the catalyst's activity in biodiesel production. Additionally, the EDXRF results showed the presence of other metallic element oxides, including Mg, Al, Si, Sr, Ba, Mn, Sn, and Sb, which can contribute to the catalytic activity during transesterification (Aisien *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 3: Compositions of the Calcined Clamshell Catalyst

The calcium oxide content obtained in this study (92.65 wt.%) is higher than the 70.113 wt.% reported by Kaewdaeng *et al.* (2017) for river snail shell ash. However, recent studies have reported varying CaO contents in different shell-based catalysts, such as Khatibi *et al.* (2020), who reported 95.5 wt. % CaO content in eggshell-derived catalysts. Similarly, Basumatary *et al.* (2023) reported 96.8 wt. % CaO content in cockle shell-based catalysts. These variations highlight the influence of different shell sources and calcination conditions on the final catalyst composition.

XRD Diffractogram of Clamshell

X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a widely used technique for examining the crystalline structure, composition, and crystal size of materials. In this study, XRD analysis was employed to investigate the degree of crystallization and phase composition of the calcined clamshell catalyst. The XRD diffractogram of the calcined clamshell sample is presented in Figure 4. This analysis provides valuable insights into the structural properties of the catalyst, which are essential for understanding its catalytic activity and potential applications.

Figure 4: XRD Diffractogram of the Calcined Clamshell

The XRD pattern of the calcined clamshell catalyst exhibited intense, sharp diffraction peaks at specific Bragg's angle 2θ values, confirming the presence of calcium oxide (CaO) as the dominant phase. The observed peaks at 2θ values of 22.5° , 25.25° , 29.39° , 33.50° , 39.70° , 47.40° , and 55.80° are characteristic of CaO, indicating its crystalline nature. These findings are consistent with previous studies, such as Amenaghawon *et al.* (2022), who reported similar peaks in a catalyst produced from fused crab shells and plantain peels. In addition to the dominant CaO peaks, minor peaks were observed at 39.70° , 42.69° , and 64.00° , corresponding to the presence of magnesium oxide (MgO). Furthermore, peaks at 47.40° and 68.08° indicated the presence of aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3), while a broad peak between $22-24^\circ$ suggested the presence of silicon dioxide (SiO_2). These findings are supported by the EDXRF results and are consistent

with previous reports (Amenaghawon *et al.*, 2022; Kedir *et al.*, 2023). The presence of these minor oxide phases may contribute to the catalytic activity during transesterification, enhancing the overall performance of the catalyst.

Surface Area, Pore Volume, and Pore Sizes

The surface area, pore volume, and pore size of the calcined clamshell catalyst were determined using N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms. The results are presented in Table 1, providing insight into the catalyst's textural properties. These characteristics are crucial in understanding the catalyst's performance, as they influence the accessibility of reactants to active sites and the overall reaction kinetics. The BET surface area and porosity analysis offer valuable information on the catalyst's potential for efficient transesterification reactions.

Table 1: Surface Area, Pore Volume and Pore Sizes

Sample	Surface Area (m^2/g)	Pore Volume B_{JH} (cc/g)	Pore Size B_{JH} (nm)
Clamshells	228.046	0.111	2.135

The BET analysis results for the calcined clamshell catalyst are presented in Table 1, showing the surface area, pore size, and pore volume obtained from nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms. The catalyst exhibited a high specific surface area of $228.046 m^2/g$, indicating a strong adsorption capacity. This large surface area, combined with the pore

volume and pore size, suggests that the calcined clamshell catalyst is effective for transesterification reactions. The high surface area and porosity provide a greater number of active sites, enhancing the catalyst's performance and facilitating efficient reactant conversion.

Table 2: The Physicochemical Properties of *Hura crepitans* oil

Property	Unit	Biodiesel ASTM D6751	<i>Hura crepitans</i> Biodiesel
Specific Gravity	-	0.86 – 0.90	0.83 ± 0.001
Saponification Value	mgKOH/g	-	24.76 ± 1.3
Saponification Value	MJ/kg	-	53.69 ± 2.8
Kinematic Viscosity	mm^2/sec	1.9 – 6.0	3.43 ± 0.04
Flash Point	0C	93 min	135 ± 2.61
Cloud Point	0C	-3 – 12	8.36 ± 0.57
Pour Point	0C	-15 – 16	-3.89 ± 0.2
Acid Value	mgKOH/g	0.05 max	0.33 ± 0.03
Sulphur Content	%	0.05 max	0.01 ± 0.001
Iodine Value	gI ₂ /100g	-	45.03 ± 0.4
Water & Sediment	%	0.05 max	0.02 ± 0.001

The results presented in Table 2 demonstrate that the biodiesel produced through the transesterification process exhibits properties that are well within the specified limits set by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM). This conformity to ASTM standards indicates that the biodiesel possesses the necessary characteristics to serve as a viable substitute for petroleum-based diesel fuel. With its

properties meeting the required standards, the produced biodiesel can be confidently utilized as an alternative fuel source, offering a promising solution for reducing dependence on fossil fuels and mitigating environmental impacts.

Fatty Acid Methyl Ester Profile of the Biodiesel Produced

The fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) composition of biodiesel produced from *Hura crepitans* oil is presented in Table 3. The major FAMES include Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester (16.15%), 9, 12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester (27.04%), and Tetradecanoic acid methyl ester (24.30%). Other notable FAMES are 11-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester (8.04%) and Octadecanoic acid methyl ester (4.49%). Minor FAMES include 7, 9-octadecadiynoate acid methyl ester, 2, 5-Octadecadiynoic acid methyl ester, and 9-Hexadecenoic acid methyl ester. The dominance

of ester compounds (81.09%) indicates the suitability of biodiesel for engine applications (Giwa *et al.*, 2022; Atabani *et al.*, 2022). The FAME composition affects biodiesel's properties, such as cetane number, viscosity, and stability (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). The presence of unsaturated FAMES (e.g., 9, 12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester) can impact oxidation stability, while saturated FAMES (e.g., Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester) can influence cetane number and cold flow properties.

Table 1: Fatty Acid Methyl Ester Profile of the Biodiesel Produced.

Name of compound	Molecular Formula	% Area
7,9-octadecadiynoate acid methyl ester	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂	0.43
2,5-Octadecadiynoic acid, methyl ester	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂	0.29
9-Hexadecenoic acid methyl ester	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O ₂	0.35
Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	16.15
9,12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂	27.04
Tetradecanoic acid methyl ester	C ₁₅ H ₃₀ O ₂	24.30
11-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂	8.04
Octadecanoic acid methyl ester	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O ₂	4.49
Other Non-Methyl ester compounds	-	18.91

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the successful production of high-quality biodiesel from *Hura crepitans* seed oil using a calcium oxide (CaO) catalyst derived from clamshells. The CaO catalyst, synthesized through calcination at 900 °C, was characterized by FTIR, EDXRF, XRD, and BET analysis, confirming its structural and compositional properties. The catalyst exhibited excellent performance in the methanolysis reaction, yielding biodiesel with fuel properties that meet the ASTM standard. The produced biodiesel's specific gravity, saponification value, higher heating value, kinematic viscosity, flash point, cloud point, pour point, acid value, and sulphur content all fell within acceptable limits. These findings suggest that the clamshell-derived CaO catalyst is a viable and efficient heterogeneous catalyst for biodiesel production, offering a promising approach for sustainable energy generation and the utilization of waste materials.

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